

Comparison of Pre Emptive-Analgesic Efficacy of Oral Flupirtine with Oral Clonidine in Diagnostic Laparoscopy

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Abstract:

Objective: Post operative pain remains a problem worldwide, resulting in delayed post operative mobility and recovery. The aim of this study was to compare analgesic efficacy of oral flupirtine maleate with oral clonidine in diagnostic laparoscopy for gynaecological procedures.

Material and Methods: This is hospital based, randomised, double blind, comparative study. After receiving approval from ethical committee, 50 cases were allocated to two groups using sealed envelope method to receive capsule flupirtine (200 mg) or clonidine (0.2 mg) orally, 1 hr prior to surgery with a sip of water. Mean of total number of rescue analgesia required, median visual analog scores (VASs) at 0, ½, 1, 2, 4, 6 hr post operatively were compared and analysed by using non parametric Mann Whitney U test using primer version 7 software.

Results: VAS score was lower during entire duration of study in flupirtine group having significant difference at 4 & 6 hrs. Requirement of rescue analgesia was comparable in both groups.

Conclusion: Flupirtine is superior to clonidine as it provide long duration of post operative analgesia without causing significant changes in hemodynamic variables and better tolerance to patient.

Keywords: Flupirtine maleate, Clonidine, NMDA receptor, NSAID, Pre emptive analgesia, Rescue analgesia, Visual analogue score.

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Introduction

Effective postoperative pain control is an essential component of the care of the surgical patient. Inadequate pain control, apart from being inhumane, may result in increased morbidity or mortality. Pre-emptive analgesia is a treatment, initiated before the surgery to prevent emergence of central sensitisation caused by incision and inflammatory injuries occurring during surgery and in early postoperative period. [1] Various drugs are available for pre emptive analgesia like non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAID's), opioids, local anaesthetics in general anaesthesia, clonidine, NMDA(N-methyl-D-aspartate) receptor antagonists. [2]

There are various methods and drugs available for pre-emptive analgesia:

NSAID's have analgesic and antipyretic effect by inhibiting cyclooxygenase enzymes reversibly and non-selectively, involved in formation of inflammatory messenger molecules (prostaglandin and thromboxane's) of inflammation. Drugs available for use are diclofenac sodium, celecoxib, parecoxib, and

ketorolac. Their use in clinical practice is limited as pre emptive agents because of their side effects like severe gastritis, post-operative bleeding, and gastrointestinal intolerance. [3]

Opioids have profound analgesic effect through various opioid receptors in the central nervous system (CNS) for prolonged period, and they can be used through various routes (intravenous, regional) for surgical and postoperative pain relief. But when given systemically opioids are required in higher doses to prevent generation of central sensitization. The main disadvantages with opioid use are respiratory depression, sedation, bradycardia, and pruritus due to histamine release. [4]

Local anaesthetics act by inhibiting generation of action potential by inhibiting the sodium influx in voltage dependent sodium channels in the neuronal membrane. Local anaesthetics are used in nerve blocks, regional anaesthesia and wound infiltration with or without opioid for surgery. Local

anaesthetics can be used as pre-emptive analgesic agent through various routes in general anaesthesia. [5]

NMDA receptors are more abundantly present in dorsal horn of spinal cord and are involved in transmitting the nociceptive impulses from afferent fibres, to the higher centre. Blockade of these receptors leads to prevention of central sensitisation and postoperative pain. Drugs available for pre-emptive analgesia are ketamine, dextromethorphan and flupirtine. Flupirtine is indirectly acting NMDA receptor antagonist. [6]

Clonidine is a centrally acting selective partial alpha 2 adrenergic agonists with selectivity of 200:1 in favour of alpha 2 receptors that has a variety of different actions including antihypertensive as well as the ability to potentiate the effects of local anaesthetics and pain relief by an opioid independent mechanism. Its primary effect is sympatholytic and it reduces peripheral norepinephrine release by stimulation of the prejunctional inhibitory α_2 adrenoreceptors in the peripheral and spinal neurons. The purpose of this study is to compare analgesic efficacy of oral flupirtine and oral clonidine as pre-emptive agents. [7]

Materials and Methods

This is hospital based, randomised, double blind, comparative study conducted in Department of Anaesthesia Zenana hospital, S.M.S. Medical college, Jaipur, for duration of eight months January 2018 to August 2018, after due permission from the institutional ethics committee and research review board and written informed consent from every patient. 50 eligible cases were allocated randomly into two study groups using opaque sealed envelope method. Both drugs were given to patients in same brown colour envelopes. Drug envelopes were prepared and drug given to patient by my colleague not participating in study to avoid biasing.

Patients were randomly allocated into two groups:

- Group (A) n= 25: patients in whom oral flupirtine 200 mg was given.
- Group (B) n= 25: patients in whom oral clonidine 0.2 mg was given.

Eligibility Criteria: Every patient was screened a day before surgery after applying inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Written Informed consent.
- Age between 20-50 years.
- Patient with ASA class I or II.
- Patient body weight between 35-60 Kg.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients not willing to participate in the study.
- Patients in whom general anaesthesia is contraindicated.
- Patient allergic to flupirtine /clonidine or diclofenac.
- Patients of tuberculosis, renal, liver, thyroid diseases.
- Patients with history of intake of any analgesic drug within two days prior to surgery.

For selected patients monitors attached – non-invasive blood pressure (NIBP), SpO₂, ECG, EtCO₂ pulse rate. 20 Gauge intravenous line secured. Pre-medication given- iv injection ranitidine 1mg/kg + inj metoclopramide 0.2mg/kg + inj glycopyrrolate 5mcg/kg + inj midazolam 0.02 mg/kg + inj. Fentanyl 1-2mcg/kg. Then pre oxygenation done with 100% oxygen for 3 minutes followed by induction with iv Propofol 2mg/kg+ succinylcholine 2mg/kg body weight. Oral intubation done with proper size endotracheal tube. For maintenance nitrous oxide + oxygen(60%+40%), isoflurane, inj atracurium SOS given. And after completion of surgery reversal done with inj neostigmine 0.05 mg/kg+ inj glycopyrrolate 0.01mg/kg intravenously, followed by extubation.

Patients were assessed for pain using VAS score and sedation at 0, 1/2, 1, 2, 4, 6 hour, need of rescue analgesia, and adverse effects. (Zero hour is considered from 10 minutes after extubation). Patients were allowed to receive Injection Diclofenac 75 mg iv as rescue analgesia on VAS of more than 3, in addition on demand rescue analgesia was also offered to patients.

Observation chart

Table 1: Demographic variables

Variables	Group A	Group B	P value
ASA 1/11	21/4	20/5	1.000(NS)
Age(years)	35.9±7.4	34.8±4.2	0.518(NS)
Weight(Kgs)	50.4±10.6	52.7±5.5	0.345(NS)
Height(Cms)	154.2±6.4	152.7±5.2	0.375(NS)
Duration of surgery(</> 30 min)	3/22	3/22	0.663(NS)

Table 2: Comparison of vas score among study groups

Time	Group A	Group B	P value
0 hour	0.48±0.50	0.72±0.45	0.174(NS)
½ hour	1.20±0.57	1.44±0.50	0.217(NS)
1 hour	1.90±0.67	2.40±0.67	0.054(NS)
2 hour	1.92±0.64	2.52±0.71	0.992(NS)
4 hour	2.40±0.57	3.08±0.75	<0.003(S)
6 hour	2.68±0.50	3.40±0.70	<0.004(S)

P value calculated using Mann Whitney rank sum test.

Table 3: Comparison of number of patients requiring rescue analgesia among study groups

Rescue analgesia required within 6 hrs	Group A		Group B		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Yes	4	16	8	28	12	22
No	21	84	17	72	38	78
Total	25	100	25	100	50	100

Chi-Square = 0.833 with 1 degree of freedom; P= 0.361(NS)

Table 4: comparison of sedation score among study group

Time	Group A	Group B	P value
0 hr	2.08 ±0.27	2.44 ±0.51	0.029 (S)
½ hr	1.92 ± 0.27	2.28 ± 0.54	0.043 (S)
1 hr	1.76±0.43	2.20±0.50	0.020 (S)
2 hr	1.72± 0.46	1.76± 0.44	0.815(NS)
4 hr	1.56± 0.50	1.44 ± 0.51	0.472 (NS)
6 hr	1.44±0.50	1.12±0.33	0.53 (NS)

Results

No significant difference was observed in demographic characteristics between both groups (table 1). Group A exhibited lower VAS score as compared to group B throughout study having significant difference at 4hrs and 6 hrs (p value <0.05), while VAS at other time interval (0,1/2,1,2 hrs) was also lesser in group A than group B but statistically insignificant (table-2). 8 patients (28%) in group B required rescue analgesia while 4 patients (16%) from group A required rescue analgesia(table-3). The sedation scores at 0, 1/2, 1 hrs post-operatively were better in Group A as compared to Group B (p value<0.05) while there is no significant difference at 2, 4 and 6 hrs (table-4). The mean baseline variables i.e. pulse rate, systolic & diastolic blood pressure, mean arterial pressure, saturation was comparable in both the groups.

Statistical analysis:

Quantitative or Continuous variables like age, weight, height were expressed as mean and standard deviation and were analysed using student t test and Ordinal variables like VAS score and sedation score were analysed using non parametric Mann Whitney U test using primer version 7 software. A p value < 0.05 was taken as statistically significant.

Discussion

Preemptive analgesia prevents hypersensitization by decreasing nociceptive impulse during surgery, thereby provides adequate perioperative and post-operative analgesia. We have compared flupirtine and clonidine as pre emptive analgesic drugs in respect to their efficacy of post operative pain control, post operative sedation and requirements of rescue analgesia. Flupirtine is derived from tri aminopyridine compound. [8] It has been used for treatment of pain arising from surgery, trauma, tooth extraction, dysmenorrhea, migraine, joint diseases, muscle spasm and cancer for past 25 years in Europe. Flupirtine acts as an indirectly acting NMDA receptor antagonist by opening the K⁺ channels. It antagonises NMDA receptor induced glutamate mediated increase in intracellular calcium ion concentration in dose dependent manner. Then it binds with G protein coupled receptor in neuronal cell membrane and activates the K⁺ channels. This activation of K⁺ channels lead to increase in intracellular K⁺ ion concentration, then hyperpolarisation of neuronal cell membrane. These neuronal cells become less excited. This opening of K⁺ channels indirectly suppress the NMDA receptor activation. This action blocks the transmission of nociceptive impulses. The drugs opening these neuronal K⁺ channels are called as "selective

neuronal potassium channel openers" (SNEPCO. Flupirtine is prototype of SNEPCO. [9]

Clonidine is a prototype, partially selective alpha-2 agonist ($\alpha_2: \alpha_1 = 220:1$). It is a centrally acting imidazole compound. It is used as a pre- anaesthetic medication through oral or intravenous route and it provides sedation, anxiolysis, anti-sialagogue effect, decreases doses of anaesthetic drugs, attenuates the hemodynamic responses to laryngoscopy and intubation, decreases intraoperative lability of blood pressure and heart rate, decreases MAC (mean alveolar concentration) of volatile agents, provides analgesia and reduces post-operative shivering. [10]

When the two groups were compared, it was found that Patients in Group A exhibited lower VAS score as compared to Group B. Statistically significant difference was observed at 4 hrs and 6 hrs (p value <0.05). Similar findings were observed in studies of Singh S et al Yadav G et al Thapa D et al and Mossaffa F et al. Rescue analgesic requirement within 6 hrs was noted in 4 patients of Group A & 8 (28%) patients of Group B. Our study results were similar previous studies of Yadav G et al and Mathur. R et al. Haemodynamically stability was similar with both drugs without any serious effect, and Singh S et al study on clonidine and Das A et al study on flupirtine showed similar results. [11]

Das A et al did evaluation of preoperative flupirtine in ambulatory functional endoscopic sinus surgery in a prospective, double-blind, randomized controlled trial. Postanesthesia Care Unit (PACU) and hospital stay, hemodynamic parameters, and side effects were all recorded for each patient. Group F patients suffered significantly less nasal bleeding and surgeon's satisfaction score was also high in this group. Discharge time from PACU and hospital was similar between two groups without any appreciable side effects. To conclude, flupirtine as a premedication found to be providing more favorable perioperative hemodynamic conditions, analgesia and thus allowing less nasal bleeding as well as more surgeons' satisfaction score. [12]

Mathur R et al did comparison of effect of pre-emptive use of oral flupirtine and oral pregabalin for post operative analgesia in abdominal hysterectomy, whereas Jesus RR evaluated therapy for acute pain relief after laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Their objective was to identify the best therapeutic strategy available to the anesthesiologist for the acute postoperative pain of patients submitted to elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy. They concluded that there is no consensus as to the best analgesic strategy to be implemented in the acute postoperative pain of laparoscopic cholecystectomy, which requires its applicability in an individualized way, based on the scientific evidence found in the literature. As contribution to medical learning and practice, we point out the theoretical enrichment of

the analgesic drug options available for the therapy of postoperative pain in patients submitted to elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy, and alert the team to consider the adverse effects of the interventions implemented. [13]

Priya L et al did a study, aim of this study was to analyze the outcome by surgical management of clavicle midshaft fractures by locking plate. This study shows stable fixation with locking compression plate and screws for displaced middle-third clavicle fracture gives immediate relief of pain, prevents the development of shoulder stiffness, and helps in early rehabilitation

Conclusion

Pre-emptive use of both flupirtine 200 mg and clonidine 0.2 mg orally are effective for prolongation of post-operative analgesia but flupirtine 200 mg is superior to clonidine 0.2 mg as it provides long duration of post- operative analgesia without causing significant change in hemodynamic variables and better tolerance to patient. Although this is a short study conducted over 50 patients, we conclude that flupirtine 200 mg is better drug for pre-emptive analgesia and it can be used safely as a part of multimodal analgesia regimen.

Declarations:

Funding: None **Conflicts of interest/Competing interests:** None **Availability of data and material:** Department of Anaesthesia Zenana hospital, S.M.S. Medical college, Jaipur **Code availability:** Not applicable **Consent to participate:** Consent taken **Ethical Consideration:** There are no ethical conflicts related to this study. **Consent for publication:** Consent taken

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